

波粒二象性到底是如何产生的？用系统全局的思维 方式去理解波粒二象性

How exactly does wave-particle duality arise?

Understand wave-particle duality in a systematic and
global way of thinking

电磁波（光）是由互相垂直的电场与磁场，在空间中相互转换发射的震荡粒子波。电磁波类似于波动，但传递过程中并无形态意义上的波动，而是沿电场方向传递的（详细理论见《三元平衡定律》），是电场和磁场以类似于能量相互转换的形式，而形成的震荡，通过周期性震荡而形成的“类波粒子”（真实状态为，电场与磁场呈周期性转换的微观系统）。

Electromagnetic wave (light) is a shock particle wave emitted by the electric field and the magnetic field vertical to each other in space. Electromagnetic wave is similar to fluctuations, but there is no morphological fluctuations in the process of transmission, but along the direction of the electric field transfer (see the law of ternary equilibrium detailed theory), is the electric field and magnetic field in the form of similar to energy conversion, and the formation of shock, through periodic shock and formation of "wave particles" (real state, electric field and magnetic field periodic conversion microscopic system).

电磁波在一个波动频率中，电场由强变弱再由弱变强，呈周期性变化，变化电场周围会形成一个围绕它的磁场。当电场由强变弱时，围绕它的磁场则由弱变强，当电场由弱变强时，围绕它的磁场则由强变弱。

Electromagnetic wave in a fluctuating frequency, the electric field from strong to weak and then from weak to strong, periodic change, change electric field will form a magnetic field around it. When the electric field changes from strong to weak, the magnetic field around it changes from weak to strong, and when the magnetic field around it changes from weak to weak.

除了电磁波（光）之外，宇宙中的一切波动现象、物体间相互作用都必须遵循“三元平衡定律”。也就是说，宇宙中所有的波必然是一种“三元平衡系统”，但“三元平衡系统”不一定是波。而电磁波、电子波、基本粒子、包括普通物质等等，就是典型的“三元平衡系统”，却又不是真正意义上的波。

With the exception of electromagnetic waves (light), all fluctuations and interactions in the universe must follow the "law of ternary equilibrium". That is to say, all the waves in the universe must be a "ternary equilibrium system", but a "ternary equilibrium system" is not necessarily a wave. Electromagnetic waves, electronic waves, elementary particles, including ordinary matter and so on are typical "ternary equilibrium systems", but not waves in the real sense.

只不过电磁波（光）是这类“三元平衡系统”中最基础的一类，电子波、基本粒子、物质等等，则是更加复杂的系统，因此这类“三元平衡系统”其实都具有“波粒二象性”。由于电磁波（光）是这类“三元平衡系统”中最基础的一种，所以其“波粒二象性”最明显，而普通物质的“波粒二象性”最弱甚至难以被科学家发现而已。

But the electromagnetic wave (light) is the most basic type of this kind of "ternary balance system", electron wave, elementary particles, matter, etc., are more complex systems, so this kind of "ternary balance system" actually has "wave-particle duality". Because electromagnetic wave (light) is one of the most basic of this "ternary balance system", its "wave particle duality" is the most obvious, and the "wave particle duality" of ordinary matter is the weakest and even difficult to be discovered by scientists.

三元平衡定律：在一个系统内，两个非平衡状态趋向于平衡状态的过程，就是三元平衡的过程。

Law of ternary equilibrium: in a system, the process of two non-equilibrium states tending to the equilibrium state, is the process of ternary equilibrium.

在电磁波的三元平衡中，电场和磁场分别为两个非平衡因素，在电磁波中，电场和磁场的这两种能量的关系，类似于水波中在波峰和波谷位置的两

种势能，在水波中波峰处的势能与波谷处的势能，呈周期性的相互转换，而最终形成水波。

In the ternary equilibrium of electromagnetic wave, electric field and magnetic field are two non-equilibrium factors, in the electromagnetic wave, the electric field and magnetic field of the two energy relationship, similar to the water wave in the peak and the trough of the two kinds of potential energy, in the wave peak of the potential energy and trough potential energy, a periodic conversion, and eventually form the water wave.

电场转化为磁场的过程和磁场转换为电场的过程，就是变化的磁场和变化的电场（能量转移或转换的过程），类似于水波中变化的动能（势能转移或转换的过程）。即在水波中相当于由波峰到波谷的向下的动能，和波谷到波峰向上的动能，动能大小与势能大小呈此消彼长的关系。

The process of converting electric field into magnetic field and the process of converting magnetic field into electric field are the changing magnetic field (the process of energy transfer or conversion), similar to the changing kinetic energy in water wave (potential energy transfer or conversion process). That is, in the water wave, the kinetic energy is equivalent to the downward kinetic energy from the peak to the trough, and the kinetic energy from the

trough to the peak of the kinetic energy and the size of the potential energy.

在电磁波中的电场和磁场，就是一对以波动形式周期性相互转换的非平衡状态，这种以波的形式周期性相互转换的状态，就是非平衡趋于平衡的状态。所以电磁波其实就是电场与磁场的三元平衡状态，这是一种最基础的三元平衡状态，同样也是最基础的三元平衡系统。

The electric field and magnetic field in the electromagnetic wave are a pair of non-equilibrium states in the form of fluctuations. This state in the form of waves is non-equilibrium going to equilibrium. So the electromagnetic wave is actually the ternary equilibrium state of electric field and magnetic field, which is the most basic ternary equilibrium state, and also the most basic ternary equilibrium system.

但是又由于电磁波并非是一般理解的波，即电磁波并非一般意义上的横波，也不是一般意义上的纵波。因为一般意义上，无论横波还是纵波都是一种机械波，机械波都是两种非平衡作用力形成的能量（包括势能和动能），交替转换形成的波。而这种通过非平衡作用力形成的波，往往都需要通过介质才能传递。而形成电磁波的两个非平衡因素，都与作用力形成的能量不同，而是电场和磁场本身，所以电磁波是通过电磁辐射传播的波，不需要通过某种介质来传递。

But also because the electromagnetic wave is not the general understanding of the wave, that is, the electromagnetic wave is not the general sense of the transverse wave, also is not the general sense of the longitudinal wave. In general, both horizontal wave and vertical wave are a mechanical wave. The mechanical wave is the energy formed by two unbalanced forces (including potential energy and kinetic energy), and the wave formed by alternating conversion. Such waves formed by non-equilibrium forces often need to be transmitted through the medium. The two non-equilibrium factors that form the electromagnetic wave are different from the energy formed by the force, but the electric field and the magnetic field itself, so the electromagnetic wave is transmitted through the electromagnetic radiation, and does not need to be transmitted through some medium.

图，电磁波的波动形态模型图，电场和磁场交替增强或减弱，二者的波动关系是一种相互转化的关系，变化互为因果。电磁波以粒子（微观系统）的形态传播，但是这种粒子又呈现周期性变化，磁场和电场周期性转换，使得电磁波呈现出波粒二象性。

Figure, the fluctuation pattern model diagram of the electromagnetic wave, the electric field and the magnetic field alternately enhance or weaken, the fluctuation relationship of the two is a kind of mutual transformation relationship, the changes are mutually causal. Electromagnetic waves propagate in the form of

particles (microscopic system), but such particles show periodic changes, and the magnetic field and electric field periodically convert, making the electromagnetic waves show wave-particle duality.

电磁波的传播方向和传递速度只和电场的方向有直接关系，和磁场的方向无直接关系，但磁场可以影响电磁波的传播方向。（关于电磁波的传递方向和传递速度的问题，在《三元平衡定律》一书中有详细的理论论述）。

The propagation direction and transmission speed of the electromagnetic wave are only directly related to the direction of the electric field, and are not directly related to the direction of the magnetic field, but the magnetic field can affect the propagation direction of the electromagnetic wave.(On the direction of transmission and speed of electromagnetic waves, detailed in the Law of Ternary Balance).

《三元平衡定律》下载: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4539809>